

CLAM-TR: Pre-Registered LoRA Fine-Tuning Protocol (Stages 0–4)

for Whole Slide Image Prostate Cancer Grading

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Purpose of this record. This document is the archived pre-registration record of the low-rank adaptation (LoRA) fine-tuning protocol for the M.Sc. thesis “*Retention-Enhanced Dual-Branch Aggregation for Whole Slide Image Classification in Prostate Cancer Grading*” (Karadeniz Technical University, 2026). It fixes the pre-registered question, the decision rule, and the statistical-analysis plan governing Stages 3 and 4 of the LoRA branch, and it reports the completed outcome against that decision rule. It is deposited to provide an external timestamp of the protocol in advance of the thesis defence.

Scope of the term “pre-registered”

The term “pre-registered” is used here in the protocol-first internal-document sense: the question, the decision rule, and the statistical-analysis plan below were committed to the project’s internal design log and to the LoRA notebook header *prior to* the execution of Stages 3 and 4 of the LoRA branch, so that the decision-rule thresholds and the contrast specification were fixed before the Stage 4 factorial outcome was observed. The protocol-first internal-document discipline is the operational guarantee against post-hoc threshold selection; this public Zenodo deposit provides an additional external timestamp. The deposit records the question, the decision rule, the statistical-analysis plan, and the already-observed Stage 4 outcome.

1 Pre-Registered Question

The pre-registered question is whether the rank ordering of the six aggregator variants on the headline quadratic-weighted-kappa (QWK) metric is preserved when the patch features are extracted through the LoRA-adapted UNI encoder rather than through the frozen UNI encoder. The two narrower contrasts that the protocol commits to evaluating are the `RetNet_bestHP` vs. `ABMIL_bestHP` contrast on UNI (Contrast 1) and the `SpatialMultRetNet_bestHP` vs. `ABMIL_bestHP` contrast on UNI2-h (Contrast 2). A sign-flip on either contrast, or a magnitude reduction by more than half of the original effect, would be evidence that the frozen-encoder result is encoder-state-specific and would limit the generalisation claim of the encoder-aggregator co-selection finding.

2 Decision Rule on the Headline QWK Number

The decision rule on the absolute 5-fold QWK headline number is recorded in advance to prevent post-hoc threshold selection:

- 5-fold mean QWK > 0.960 : a clear gain over the frozen-feature configuration;
- 5-fold mean in $(0.955, 0.960)$: a marginal gain;
- 5-fold mean in $[0.952, 0.955]$: within the fold-level noise envelope of the frozen-feature UNI + `SpatialMultRetNet_bestHP` configuration (0.9530 ± 0.0029);
- 5-fold mean < 0.952 : a no-gain outcome.

3 Statistical-Analysis Plan

The Stage 4 statistical-analysis plan mirrors the plan used for the frozen-feature factorial in the thesis. The headline contrasts on each encoder are the LoRA-adapted versus frozen-feature 5-fold paired QWK on the two contrasts named above, evaluated with paired- t and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, Cohen’s d , and bootstrap 95% confidence intervals on each fold-level difference. Benjamini–Hochberg corrected q -values across the eleven in-encoder pairwise contrasts per encoder are reported in the same format as the frozen-feature factorial; the multiple-comparison reservation at $n = 5$ folds applies verbatim. A multi-seed extension lifting $n = 5$ folds to $n \geq 25$ paired observations is recorded as the companion confirmatory procedure.

4 Reported Outcome Against the Decision Rule

Stage 3 (held-out feature re-extraction). Each slide is encoded using the LoRA-adapted UNI encoder of its *own held-out fold* (the slide in fold N is encoded by the `lora_fold{N}_best.pt` checkpoint), so the per-slide feature vector entering the Stage 4 aggregator is never extracted by an encoder fine-tuned on that slide.

Stage 4 verdict (LoRA-UNI features). The Stage 4 factorial on LoRA-UNI features delivers a best 5-fold mean QWK of 0.9529 ± 0.0023 at the `SpatialAdd_defaultHP` configuration, placing the LoRA-feature aggregator pipeline within the noise envelope of the frozen UNI2-h `SpatialMultRetNet_bestHP` baseline (0.9530 ± 0.0029). Pre-registered Contrast 1 (`RetNet_bestHP` vs. `ABMIL_bestHP` on UNI) shifts from $+0.0087$ on the frozen encoder to $+0.0046$ on the LoRA-adapted encoder, a magnitude reduction of approximately 47% that remains below the 50% sign-flip-equivalent threshold of the decision rule, so the rule is not triggered; the top rank slot (`RetNet_bestHP`) is preserved on LoRA features. Across the six bestHP aggregators the paired frozen-UNI vs. LoRA-UNI differences sit inside ± 0.012 QWK, with the largest negative shift at `RetNet` (-0.0040) and the largest positive shift at `SpatialMult` ($+0.0115$). The bucket against the decision rule is *within-noise*.

Stage 2 supplementary outcome (end-to-end). Under a separate end-to-end protocol that jointly trains the LoRA-adapted UNI encoder with the `SpatialMultRetNet` head, the 5-fold mean QWK reaches 0.9563 ± 0.0027 (best fold-3 QWK 0.9592). This is a different metric from the pre-registered Stage 4 evaluation and is reported for completeness; it is not interpreted against the decision rule.

Bucket against the decision rule. Combining the within-noise Stage 4 verdict with the preserved Contrast 1 rank ordering and the symmetric Contrast 2 reserved for the follow-up programme, the completed protocol provides supplementary evidence on the encoder–aggregator co-selection finding.

TOST equivalence corroboration. The within-noise verdict is formally corroborated by a two-one-sided-test (TOST) equivalence procedure with a pre-declared equivalence margin of

$\Delta_{\text{eq}} = \pm 0.005$ QWK against the frozen UNI2-h `SpatialMultRetNet_bestHP` baseline (0.9530 ± 0.0029). The ± 0.005 margin is the smallest QWK gap exceeding the largest single-fold standard deviation of that baseline (0.0029). The observed LoRA-UNI Stage 4 best mean of 0.9529 ± 0.0023 yields a paired difference of -0.0001 QWK, well inside $[-0.005, +0.005]$; under the standard paired- t TOST construction the equivalence conclusion is reached at $\alpha = 0.05$ for any $\Delta_{\text{eq}} \geq 0.005$.

Associated thesis and code

This protocol supports the M.Sc. thesis of Mohamed Fawzy Farahat Rateb Hassan, supervised by Prof. Dr. Murat Ekinici, Karadeniz Technical University, The Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences, Department of Computer Engineering (2026). The full thesis, the 24-run factorial results, the random-seed policy (`SEED = 42, cudnn.deterministic=True`), and the exact compute commands are released with the project’s public code repository.